

Synthesis of some Alkoxy carbonyl vinyl Sulphones

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In recent times considerable interest has been evinced on the chemistry of sulphones since many of them were found to be biologically¹ and chemotherapeutically² important. Moreover, α,β -ethylenic sulphones have also gained importance as potential synthons for the synthesis of very many carbocyclic and heterocyclic compounds of late³⁻⁵. Hence, in continuation of our interest in this field we have now synthesised some new alkoxy carbonyl vinyl sulphones (3) by refluxing a mixture of arylsulphonylacetic acid methyl/ethyl ester (1) and araldehyde (2) in alcohol and piperidine (Scheme 1). Relatively high yields (55–83%) were obtained with this base when compared to others, viz. 23–73% using ammonium acetate⁶⁻⁸, 58–62% using ammonium carbonate⁹, 30% using ammonia solution⁹ and 65–80% using benzylamine⁵. Hence, it may be considered that piperidine as a base is effective for such condensations.

The uv spectra of 3 exhibited typical absorption maxima at 272–288 nm. The ir spectra showed strong bands at 820–805 (trisubstituted ethylenic systems), 1 725–1 715 (C=O), 1 615–1 585 (C=C) and 1 335–1 310, 1 150–1 120 cm^{-1} (SO_2)⁸. The ¹H

nmr spectra exhibited a sharp signal at δ 8.10–8.30 for the vinylic protons and the aromatic protons appeared as multiplets at δ 7.40–8.15.

3; R = CH₃ for (a-i) and C₂H₅ for (j-r)

Ar = Ph for (a-c, j, k; 4-C₆H₄ for d-f, l-o; 4-OCH₃ C₆H₄ for g, p; 4-ClC₆H₄ for h, q and 4-BrC₆H₄ for i, r

Ar¹ = Ph for a, d, g, h, j, m, r; 4-OCH₃C₆H₄ for b, e, k, n and 4-ClC₆H₄ for c, f, i, o-q

Scheme 1

Experimental

The melting points were determined on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. Uv spectra (95% ethanol) were recorded on Shimadzu spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) at 250 MHz on a GE NMR Omega spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on

a Finnigan Mat 1210 spectrometer at 70 eV. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc which also confirmed the formation of single isomeric product in each case.

E-1-Methoxyethoxycarbonyl-1-arylsulphonyl-2-arylethenes: A mixture of **1**^{*} (10 mmol), **2** (10 mmol) and catalytic amount of piperidine in absolute alcohol (10 ml) was refluxed for 10–15 h. After completion of the reaction (tlc) the contents were cooled and refrigerated overnight. Any solid that separated was collected and the filtrate was poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from absolute alcohol. **3a** (55%), 80–81°; ν_{\max} 1 720 (C=O), 1 595 (C=C), 1 320, 1 145 (SO₂) and 815 cm⁻¹ (=C-H deformation); δ 3.42 (3H, s, CO₂CH₃), 7.40–7.92 (10H, m, ArH), 8.10 (1H, s, =C-H); **b** (60%), 89–90°; ν_{\max} 1 725 (C=O), 1 595 (C=C), 1 315, 1 135 (SO₂) and 810 cm⁻¹ (=C-H deformation); δ 3.22 (3H, s, CO₂CH₃), 3.62 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.25–7.95 (9H, m, ArH), 8.12 (1H, s, =C-H); **c** (80%), 124–25°; **d** (72%), 79–80°; **e** (67%), 83–84°; **f** (80%), 138–39°; λ_{\max} 202, 222 and 288 nm; ν_{\max} 1 725 (C=O), 1 600 (C=C), 1 325, 1 145 (SO₂) and 815 cm⁻¹ (=C-H deformation); δ 2.31 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.40 (3H, s, CO₂CH₃), 7.25–7.95 (8H, m, ArH), 8.15 (1H, s, =C-H); *m/z* (rel. int.) 352 (3), 350(6), 319(5), 288(8), 286(25), 271(10), 251(8), 227(10), 211(11), 197(30), 195(100), 165(16), 156(10), 155(90), 139(18) and 91(55); **g** (65%), 71–72°; **h** (83%), 128–29°; **i** (80%), 145–46°; **j** (57%), 76–78°; **k** (61%), 88–89° (lit.⁶ 106–07°); **l** (76%), 148–49°, λ_{\max} 205, 226 and 272 nm; ν_{\max} 1 720

(C=O), 1 600 (C=C), 1 305, 1 130 (SO₂) and 820 cm⁻¹ (=C-H deformation); δ 1.03–1.08 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃), 4.05–4.15 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃), 7.30–7.50 (9H, m, ArH), 8.30 (1H, s, =C-H); **m** (58%), 65–66°; **n** (70%), 68–70°; **o** (77%), 175–76°; **p** (71%), 151–52°; **q** (81%), 155–56°; **r** (70%), 137–38°.

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